

Tasks – Feedback welcome

[NFDI4Earth](#) is a community-driven process providing researchers with FAIR, coherent, and open access to all relevant Earth System Science data, to innovative research data management and data science methods.

The [OneStop4All](#) is the web-based key entry point for all NFDI4Earth content and resources, developed in a user-centered design to fit the needs of a wide range of users from different scientific domains.

We would like to **invite you to try out the OneStop4All and give feedback** so that we can adapt and improve the portal based on the community's needs. You can also use our [explanatory video](#) of the OneStop4All first if you would like an overview.

How to give feedback about the OneStop4All:

There is a feedback link at the top of the OneStop4All page. This triggers a User Support Network (USN) ticket in a dedicated feedback queue. Minor technical issues can be solved easily, issues about features and functionalities will be reviewed and prioritised for following improvement cycles of the portal.

Explore OneStop4All by 3 mini tasks! *(see next page)*

We prepared 3 tasks for you to try out and we welcome any feedback that you notice about the OneStop4All when you try to solve them. This includes issues such as functionalities, usability, descriptions, features, technical issues, things you liked, ideas for improvement, ... (Of course you can also give us feedback to anything else you notice outside the tasks...).

<https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/>

Task 1:

Find a suitable repository to publish your Earth System Science (ESS) data

- Either consider data from your own field of research or imagine you have data from an ESS discipline if you do not produce data yourself.
- Use the OneStop4All to figure out which repository could be suitable for your data.
- Did you manage to find a satisfactory solution?
- Please give us feedback on everything you notice in your search (also let us know if you tested different features to reach your goal).

Task 2:

Find out how to work with “raster data”

- Imagine you want to work with raster data but don't have much experience with it.
- Please try to find resources on the OneStop4All that will help you to complete your task.
- Let us know everything you notice along the way.

Task 3:

Search for everything available related to your own research interest

- Whatever your field of research or interest is, try to find all resources that are available within NFDI4Earth via the OneStop4All.
- Please let us know everything you notice, also if you miss anything that you would have expected to find.

Share your experience via the feedback link reachable on the portal!

THANK YOU FOR YOUR FEEDBACK!!